

Religion in the Mittani Empire

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The Mittani people were composed of a Late Bronze Age Hurrian-speaking set of communities, situated in the region around the Euphrates river between modern-day Aleppo, Erbil and Diyarbakır. At its peak in the 14th century BCE, the Mittani Empire or state would have included at least Aššur, Alalah, Arrapha, Kizzuwatna, Tunip, and probably Yamhad and Hana. These were semi-independent, and sometimes ruled by their own Kings under the overlordship of Mittani with models of governance probably adapted on a case-by-case basis. This region has been difficult to access in recent times, which means that many potentially Mittani sites remain unexcavated and much about Mittani is still unknown. To complicate matters further, in the past data about Mittani and Assyria were often added together, and to date no large (royal) Mittani archive has been identified. A huge number of mostly economic documents is available from Nuzi, which was part of the Mittani vassal state of Arrapha – but it should not be assumed that any religious practices we can discern from these for Nuzi would reflect those of the entire Mittani Empire. There is only a handful of published cuneiform tablets that can be said with certainty to have been Mittani. The biggest source of information is perhaps the Mittani series of Amarna letters, and Mittani is also frequently mentioned in other contemporary letters and treaties, e.g. by the Assyrians and Hittites. Also significant are the so-called 'Assyro-Mittani' tablets found at Boğazköy, which describe witchcraft and rituals. It is usually unclear however who wrote these, when, and where – and as with Nuzi, it should not be assumed that the practices described in these texts would have consistently applied across the entire Mittani Empire. While it is likely that the Mittani people would have primarily identified as Hurrian, not all Hurrians were Mittani. In addition, the Hurrians did not necessarily have homogenous theology, mythology, cults or rituals nor did they have a name for their religion – and as such should not be understood as a religious group. With that said – many people likely believed in a particular array of named deities, and held a related collection of beliefs with associated institutions and practices. For instance, Hurrian texts refer to an idea of heaven, earth and the underworld. The most significant Hurrian deity was the weather god Teššub. He would have yielded storm, rain, and lightning, and travelled the skies in a chariot drawn by bulls. He was joined by the goddess of love and war, Šauska, who would have played an important role e.g. blessing marriages. There were likely also a sun and mood god, Šimike and Kušuh, linked to different omens and oaths; and of course many deities, such as Nergal and Ea, borrowed from other traditions. Deities were anthropomorphic and they were given offerings. Rituals, festivals, divination and incantation all played important roles in society, and cities had temples dedicated to deities. Many more details are available about Hurrian religious beliefs, but not necessarily from Mittani sources or the Mittani period.

Date Range: 1550 BCE - 1350 BCE

Region: Mittani Empire

Region tags: Syria, Northern Iraq, Turkey, Kurdistan

A rough indication of Mittani territory during the Late Bronze Age (c. 1350 BCE).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110266412/html?lang=en>

– Source 2: https://archive.org/stream/WilhelmHurrians/Wilhelm_Hurrians_djvu.txt

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/x14269>

– Source 1 Description: Mittanian collection of the British Museum

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/HPM/index.php>

– Source 1 Description: An online database of primary source material (cuneiform texts, including Hurrian texts)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Mittani Empire was in close contact with the Hittite Empire, Assyrians, Babylonians, Egypt, as well as Arzawa and Alashiya, and various other entities from the region of modern-day Syria and Lebanon. These relationships are well-documented in the so-called 'Amarna Letters'. It is not clear how strongly the religion of each of these states differed from one another however. Egypt and Hatti certainly had their own pantheon of deities, but some overlap can be found between all societies in this region.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Notes: Priests would have had certain rituals and ceremonies, but as far as is currently known these were not intended for assigning religious affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: Since religion was closely intertwined with all aspects of daily life, it is not clear how necessary recruitment was.

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: While an official declaration of support does not exist, in the Mittani Amarna letters - official diplomatic correspondence with Egypt - deities are commonly mentioned. For example, EA 24: "[. (and) so may] Teššup, [Šauška (and) Amanu] [our gods], though we are different, [show] us nothing but love [in their hearts!]".

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: There is no way of estimating this accurately.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– I don't know

Notes: None have been identified as such, but this does not mean it never existed. What is known, is that Hurrian priests copied works of Mesopotamian religious literature and enriched them by the identification of Hurrian with Mesopotamian gods (Wilhelm 1989).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Tombs:

– I don't know

Notes: Not many Mittani sites have so far been excavated, so this is difficult to say with certainty. However, examples exist of royal grave chambers, for the same region during a similar period. A great resource is this book: (Re-)Constructing Funerary Rituals in the Ancient Near East - Proceedings of the First International Symposium of the Tübingen Post-Graduate School "Symbols of the Dead" in May 2009, edited by Peter Pfälzner, Herbert Niehr, Ernst Pernicka and Anne Wissing.

Cemeteries:

– I don't know

Notes: Similar to above.

Temples:

– Yes

Notes: A great overview of Mittani temple architecture is given in this article: 'A Hurrian-Mitanni Temple in Müslümantepe in The Upper Tigris and New Findings' by A Y Eyyüp (<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1309737>).

Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Mittani temples would have had altars, and there is also evidence some houses may have had private altars. See A. Otto 'The Organisation of Residential Space in the Mittani Kingdom as a Mirror of Different Models of Governance' (<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110266412.33/pdf>)

Devotional markers:

– I don't know

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– I don't know

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Notes: There may have been steles or standing stones, as these were common in Mesopotamia for this period in general. See e.g. <https://mcid.mcah.columbia.edu/art-atlas/mapping-mesopotamian-monuments/monuments>. I am not aware of any for Mittani, but this is a near-contemporary Babylonian example: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/325092>.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: This was not necessarily religious, but the style was distinct to Mittani - and some will have occurred in temple context. Lions and pigs appear a lot; pigs would have been common sacrificial animals. See

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282724979_Between_Syria_and_Mesopotamia_Zoomorphic_vessels_in_tf and also

<https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/bitstream/handle/1774.2/37037/MASKEVICH-DISSERTATION-2014.pdf>.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural creatures often make appearances in Mesopotamian iconography, including societies contemporary with Mittani. Here is a great article reporting on Mittani ritual theriomorphic vessels: https://www.vorderas-archaeologie.uni-muenchen.de/forschung/projekt_syrien/literatur_bazi/2019c_oteinwag_autorski.pdf.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: See comment above. In addition, this article mentions an anthropomorphic seal - but notes there are no other Mittani examples to compare to so it may not be unique to Mittani: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26802805>. Also see this seal depicting Mittani deities however (although the museum does not state why these figures have been identified as deities!): <https://art.thewalters.org/detail/17970>.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Humans appear in Mittani art. See for instance this seal: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/327787>.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to be certain, but "spirits of the dead" are mentioned in Nuzi texts.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Lipinski (2016, 'Hurrians and Their Gods in Canaan') suggests that there may have been a concept of afterlife comparable to the Egyptian idea, which would have been a life similar to earthly life. Wilhelm (2014, *Reallexikon der Assyriologie*) says that the Hurrians would have also believed in an 'underworld', and there is reference to a separation between 'heaven' and 'earth'.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Notes: I think this would have been likely, but I can't find any information about it. See for example Wygnańska 2019, 'Burial in the Time of the Amorites: the Middle Bronze Age Burial Customs from a Mesopotamian Perspective'.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: As referred to somewhere else, it is possible this may have occurred but I am not aware of any particular instances in the case of Mittani / the Hurrians, and if it did occur it would have been rare (only in the case of select elites).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

Notes: They found some burials fairly recently at Kurd Qaburstan
<https://sites.krieger.jhu.edu/kurd-qaburstan/2014-excavations/>.

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Notes: It has been suggested that Hurrians may have included horses or even chariots in burials. I am not sure what the best reference is for this though.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: We know almost nothing about Hurrian rituals for the dead and further excavation is needed.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Notes: This is likely as it occurred in neighbouring societies, but none are currently known for Mittani. There is an entire database of Hittite monuments here that can be checked: <http://ancientworldonline.blogspot.com/2011/04/monuments-of-hittites.html>.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are examples of Mittani graves, although this may not have been understood as cemeteries in the way that we see them. There is loads of academic literature on contemporary cemetery practices, see e.g. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1111635/FULLTEXT01.pdf> for the Hittites.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: King Tushratta mentions a 'karaik' for his grandfather in one of his letters, which would probably have been a temple to the dead or some kind of mausoleum (see Wilhelm 1989).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Notes: This likely did not occur, and would have been an older tradition; but there is not enough archaeological evidence to prove or disprove it currently.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Notes: Also note that the Nuzi texts refer to figurines of the spirits of the dead.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: This was probably the weather god Teššub. A good source on this type of deity is Schwemer 2007: The Storm-Gods of the Ancient Near East (Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– I don't know

Notes: It was common for this period to see the appointment of the king by the gods as their human agent to rule over the people.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– Yes [specify]: Teshub was a storm god and god of thunder, often depicted with an axe or mace. His signature animal was a bull.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Texts tend to refer to the actions of the gods rather than their feelings.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See comment above. There is mention of wrath and anger however, so this may be likely.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: There are references to the gods tasting food offered to them, but it is not clear whether they can be hungry.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: It isn't very clear what the distinction was between supernatural beings and gods. There is a paragraph on this in Johnston 2004 (Religions of the Ancient World), page 406.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Unlikely
- ↳ In dreams:
 - I don't know

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Probable
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Probable
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: This is possible, as "The idea that the spirit continues to live beyond the death of a family member is a defining factor of ancestor worship in the Near East" (N. Laneri 2018, *Funerary Customs and Religious Practices in the Ancient Near East*). However I cannot comment on this in detail for Mittani / the Hurrians. The only reference I could find is that there are Nuzi texts which refer to "spirits of the dead".
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Creatures such as griffins and sphinxes occurred on cylinder seals. See Novak 2013, 'Upper Mesopotamia in the Mittani Period'.
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– I don't know
Notes: I couldn't find any information about this.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– I don't know
Notes: See my comments on supernatural beings above.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– I don't know
Notes: Probably but it is difficult to give details, see e.g. Geller 1990 'Taboo in Mesopotamia' for more general remarks.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– I don't know

Notes: Hygiene played an important aspect in medicine, which was intertwined with religion. I do not believe there were specific religious hygiene rituals however (e.g. washing hands before praying).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to say what 'known' means here. For example, it is likely that e.g. disease was believed as something that could be transmitted intentionally to those who had incurred the wrath of the gods; but the understanding of 'disease' and 'contagion' may have differed from how we understand it now.

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: The gods often punished people because they were angry, but it may not have always been known exactly why they were angry.
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: See my notes on the afterlife.
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Depends what you mean by 'highly emphasized'?
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:
– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):
– I don't know

Notes: The concept of celibacy existed in some forms amongst priests in ancient Mesopotamia (see for example 'nadītu' in the Sippar texts) but nothing specific is known about practices in the Mittani

Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: See above

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– I don't know

Notes: Both visual and written references to eunuchs occur in ancient Mesopotamian history, including the period of the Mittani Empire. See for example 'Men, Women, Eunuchs, Etc.: Visualities of Gendered Identities in Kassite Babylonian Seals (ca. 1470-1155 B.C.)' by Serdar Yalçın and 'Eunuchs in Hatti and Assyria: A Reassessment' by Ilan Peled.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Notes: About Hurrian / Mittani practices I am not sure, but you can have a look at Wasserman 2016, 'Fasting and Voluntary Not-Eating in Mesopotamian Sources' for more general comments. They state 'communal fasting and voluntary denial of food is unknown in ancient Mesopotamia'.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know, but I am not aware of any references to this.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Notes: Same as above; unlikely.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: There is no reference to this for Mittani / Hurrian religion as far as I am aware, but there is some evidence out there that in large state burials other Mesopotamian societies may have buried guards or maids with royals, and Assyria is known for having had a 'substitute king ritual' - see e.g. Lambert 1957.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Notes: Very unlikely. Further see Siddall 2020, 'Ritual Killing and Human Sacrifice in the Ancient Near East'.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that these were used yes, as there is reference to this more generally for this region and time, but there is very little evidence for Hurrian / Mittani to be certain.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Notes: I am not completely sure what is meant by this; but considering the scarcity of Mittani texts it would be difficult to be sure about any details of this if it was the case.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Notes: While much is uncertain, a few things are known on this subject: there are texts dating to the Mittani period that mention famine, there is archaeological evidence of famine, the social structure of the time likely included communal support, and religion and state were tied closely together. However, it is difficult to re-construct religious aid related to famine with certainty. Please see 'Obedient Bellies: Hunger and Food Security in Ancient Mesopotamia', by Seth Richardson, for further, broader, reading on food and poverty in ancient Mesopotamia.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See above. There was likely at least some degree of centralisation of food resources and control of surpluses.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Same as above two answers. A lot more is known about the elites and wealthy during this period, than there is about the poor. With that said, even the famous 'Code of Hammurabi' already included several provisions designed to protect the poor.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See above on legal systems. No such 'Code' has survived for Mittani, but legal documents dating to this region and period do exist.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: Similar again to above. Nothing specific is known for Mittani, but there is other evidence from ancient Mesopotamia for care of the elderly and infirm. See for example 'The Care of the Elderly in the Ancient Near East' by Marten Stol & Sven Peter Vleeming (eds).

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See above.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Formal, theoretical education in most of ancient Mesopotamia was almost certainly limited to the elite. Scribes and priests would have practiced memorising texts, both orally and in writing. There is evidence of pupils practicing calculations, as well as astronomy, architecture and arts. Tradespeople would have been trained in a 'mentor-mentee' relationship, for example, a parent showing their child how they work. However, it is not clear how much of this learning - apart from priesthood - was driven by religion. Many Hurrian religious texts survive from neighbouring societies, as well as 'Assyro-Mittanian' and Hittite texts from Boğazköy (Hattuša), so it can certainly be assumed that in these areas religion was intertwined with the teaching of at least scribes. However, with the current state of excavations and publications (2022) surviving Mittani texts can nearly all be classed as official letters composed by seemingly professional scribes. They do not describe education, and no obvious 'school' has so far been found. We do know that scribal education in the Mittani Empire was likely - at least mostly - centralised. In addition, we know that in nearby Arrapha - a small kingdom ruled by Mittani - scribal education occurred in a home-based or family-oriented setting. It is unclear whether there was a particular curriculum, although other societies from ancient Mesopotamia did make use of set texts. Please see 'Literacy in the Old Babylonian city of Nippur' (2020) by Robert Middeke-Conlin for a comparison.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: See above.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There was a Mittani imperial bureaucracy, so logically many aspects of daily life were intertwined with this including presumably religion.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not known how common it was for regular people to travel or interact with people outside their own community. This certainly did occur however, particularly amongst traders and the elite, so it can be assumed that there would have been interaction with other bureaucracies such as Hittite and Egyptian.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the concept of central food storage existed, because this was the case for other Mesopotamian societies (see for instance <https://oi.uchicago.edu/research/research-archives-library/dissertations/grain-storage-and-moral-economy-mesopotamia-3000>) - although it should be said most evidence dates to the 3rd millennium (well pre-Mittani), and many societies economically evolved beyond that. It is not known for Mittani whether food storage would have had any particular religious link. If it occurred it was likely part of the centralised palace/imperial system, not temples, although according to the belief system of the time there may of course have been a religious connection (i.e. there were Mesopotamian gods associated with e.g. grain).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See comment above. This article suggests there was central grain storage at Tell Brak in the 3rd millennium - which did later have Mittani occupation as well:

https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10117906/1/AL-AZEM_THESIS.pdf. Here is an article about food-

related deities for the Middle Assyrian period, which coincides with the Mittani period:

https://www.academia.edu/1033648/2011_The_food_of_the_gods_MARV_3_16_a_Middle_Assyrian_offerings_list_to_the_great_gods

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: Water management was certainly important in ancient Mesopotamia, and large amounts of evidence exist for the design of canals, dams, irrigation systems, and so forth, dating long before the Mittani period. Therefore, it is very likely the Mittani people would have also been experts in water management. However, few details are currently known about this from archaeology and literature, and any religious connection is unknown. This student thesis has some notes on Mittani irrigation and agriculture: <https://studenttheses.universiteitleiden.nl/access/item%3A2607121/view>.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See comment above.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Notes: The Mittani were known for a certain type of chariot called 'maryannu' (see e.g. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41661828>), and it is well-documented that the King sent large expeditions to Egypt with gifts. This indicates there would have been some thought put into transport infrastructure. However, in the classic sense of e.g. building roads, this was not present in ancient Mesopotamia or the Mittani Empire. Some routes would have been common and used often, and therefore it is possible to see 'paths' on satellite images (see e.g. <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/421448-revealing-bronze-age-traffic-along-roads-in-upper-mesopotamia>), but this would have had no religious connection and it is unclear whether there was any centralised planning involved in general.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See comment above. Further see this article about the Assyrians: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/sargon/essentials/governors/thekingsroad/>.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Notes: It is known that sacrificial offerings or payments were offered to deities in ancient Mesopotamia, often given to the king, palace, or temple. Little about this is known for Mittani however.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There was a tax system, which is mentioned in some documents. For example, in Mittani Alt 108 the king orders his official Utti not to impose a tax upon a trade-caravan of Niqmepa. (So although there is an exception made here, this implies that normally there would be a trade tax.)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: See comment below.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: There is a reference from Assur to an 'itu-ayyu', that may have functioned as a police corps (see https://www.ucl.ac.uk/sargon/downloads/ponchia_crai_54_2012.pdf p. 218). Furthermore, later, Neo-Babylonian 'paqūdu' has been identified with a police person of some kind, who would have pursued petty crimes in large urban centres. See <https://www.asor.org/onetoday/2015/08/policemen-in-1st-millennium-bc-babylonia/>. Further near-contemporary Assyrian and Hittite documents also refer to equivalents of police officers associated with the army. There is no direct evidence for this for the

Mittani Empire however so for the time being this question cannot be answered with certainty.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not clear whether there was any specific connection between court and temple, although this article suggests judges would have been secular: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/594119>. Do note that the article dates to 1943 so more up to date information may be available today.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There was a justice system in the Mittani Empire, although not a lot is known about this from 'pure' Mittani documents. Vassal state Arrapha however has yielded a large number of cuneiform tablets describing lawsuits - including court organisation, conduct of trials, and judgement (see e.g. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/594119>).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: See below. It is not known whether there was a religious connection to punishment, although, as stated previously, in the belief system of the time there may have been little separation between what was perceived as e.g. punishment in a court of law and punishment by the gods.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

Notes: As before, few Mittani documents survive that would be able to refer to this. However, this article gives a good overview of the death penalty in Mesopotamia more generally: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1227595> (not that it is from 1967 and further evidence may have been collected since then).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– I don't know

Notes: While not known for Mittani explicitly this is likely, as exile is mentioned in literary as well as legal texts from ancient Mesopotamia. See e.g. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25608363>.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Notes: This is also likely, as this is mentioned as early as Hammurabi's code of law and also features in later texts; again, since only a few dozen Mittani texts have been identified to date it is difficult to say anything with absolute certainty.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Notes: Unsure whether this would have differed strongly from the understanding of exile.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: While, again, this is not known for Mittani specifically, it is mentioned in the legal texts of the Mittani vassal kingdom of Arrapha. This is a generally helpful book on law and order in the Ancient Near East: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9781646021208/html>. It also includes a chapter on Nuzi.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– I don't know

Notes: See comment below.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: There is of course the famous legal code of Hammurabi, dating to the 18th century CE, that set a precedent for later societies. Indeed, there is also a near-contemporary Hittite legal code, we know of Middle Assyrian laws, and so forth. Few Mittani documents survive so it is more difficult to say anything about this with certainty, but it may be assumed there was a formal Mittani legal code too that has not yet been discovered. This page has some good notes on justice in ancient Mesopotamia in general: <https://factsanddetails.com/world/cat56/sub363/entry-6077.html>.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are regular references to the Mittani army in texts across the Near East dating to the Mittani period. It is known that the elite fought in horse-drawn chariots, and there may have also been a form of conscription for lower classes, which is mentioned in texts from Arrapha and Alalakh. Also see <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110266412.11/pdf>.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Mittani Empire likely had its own, distinct, centralised scribal schooling, resulting in a unique Mittani cuneiform script. See <https://brill.com/view/title/36251?language=en>.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See comment above. Scribes may have also written in scripts unique to Assur, Nuzi, and other locations within and near the Mittani Empire. If considering religion in particular, Ugarit and Hattusa produced a lot of religious texts with connections to Mittani.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not known whether the Mittani people would have had their own calendar, but studies of astronomy date back to very early Mesopotamian history and it is known that months and seasons were given their own names by various societies. See e.g. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/606564>. In particular, there is evidence of this from Mittani vassal Kingdom Arrapha: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41864553>. It is not clear whether there was any particular religious

connection however - apart from month names being associated with certain deities. (The same can be said about modern English: the word Friday comes from Germanic goddess Frigga, but few people are even aware of this.)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: See comment above.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– I don't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: There are no particular Mittani documents that mention this, but from other contemporary societies we know that e.g. priests would have been provided with food, and as mentioned previously it is possible there was central food storage and central food distribution.

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